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D4.7 - Demonstrator of the Data Stewardship Service

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1 Introduction

The management of research data in the health sector is highly diverse and complex due to ethical considerations, data protection regulations and multiple stakeholders, to name but a few. Although prospectively planned studies contain inherently well-structured and quality-assured research data, they are often local solutions with local data structures. Here, local may also mean a research project or a small research community, in turn making it difficult to find, link and synthesise studies. On the one hand, NFDI4Health aims to develop the information infrastructure to support and promote FAIR research data management; on the other hand, it would appear that dedicated FAIR data literate and NFDI4Health aware staff are needed to manage and curate the data collected during the research process.

In the spirit of Open Science and the requirements of research funding agencies, research data at universities and research institutions should be stored in a traceable and reusable manner. In the last few years, a new professional field has emerged for these tasks, which is often referred to as data stewardship. However, the exact roles and responsibilities of data stewards, and how data stewardship can best be implemented in institutions, have not been fully clarified (Seydlmeier et al. 2023). Research libraries can act as hubs to connect local communities of researchers, professionals and infrastructure providers to the NFDI and, in particular, to the NFDI4Health infrastructure. This highlights the role of data stewardship in providing guidance on research data management (RDM) and the role of training services as multipliers.

This pilot project aims to explore the impact of library-based data stewards working closely together with people who conduct(ed) studies and to serve as a positive practical example for other libraries or infrastructure institutions wishing to establish data stewardship for clinical and epidemiological studies. It also aims to explore the relationship between generic RDM knowledge at library or infrastructure level as well as for various disciplines within a research institution, and to then determine how this knowledge can be combined to benefit both (cf., Shutsko & Lindstädt 2020).

Regarding the tasks and embedding of data stewards, the so-called embedded or discipline-specific data steward comes into play. In addition to general issues of research data management, these individuals are primarily concerned with the specific tasks associated with their particular discipline. In this case, it is the management of data from clinical and epidemiological studies.

This pilot project describes the initial situation, the roles of data stewards on both infrastructure and research levels, and the goals of collaboration between the two. We then describe our approach, including the development of the data steward pilot. The experiences gleaned by both ZB MED (data steward for epidemiological studies) and UCL Cologne (data steward for clinical studies) will be illustrated and the main features of the two approaches will be given.

2 Initial situation

Within the NFDI4Health project, there are various Task Areas (TAs) which focus on different topics. Some TAs are responsible for the development of infrastructure and work on the development of standards for FAIR data (TA2 Standards) or the development of a data portal for clinical trials and epidemiological studies (TA3 Services). Other TAs work on the use cases (TA5 use cases), which consist of discipline-specific researchers with an epidemiological or clinical background who want to manage and publish their

data, i.e. study metadata, study documents such as questionnaires or data dictionaries, within the NFDI4Health data portal, the German Central Health Study Hub (CSH).¹ The approach applied to each of these tasks differs as the persons in these task areas have different fields of expertise. Data stewards involved with the infrastructure have generic RDM expertise and are familiar with research data, metadata, and basic research data management concepts. Discipline-specific data stewards from research, on the other hand, have less experience with generic RDM, but bring discipline-specific expertise, either from epidemiological or clinical research, when it comes to methods and workflows. Data stewards are needed for both infrastructure and research, but their profiles are very different due to their different areas of expertise. One of the first tasks of the infrastructure stewards was to develop a publication policy.² This is a document that assists and guides researchers who wish to publish their metadata and study documents on the CSH. It lists the types of documents which can be published and a seven-step process illustrating all of the steps necessary for publication. A metadata schema has also been developed to describe the published data and implemented in the CSH metadata input screen to ensure the collection of rich metadata.

Testing the CSH input screen along with the search and filter functions of published documents is another task for data stewards, who help to improve this service. In doing so, data stewards gain knowledge about the service, which they can then pass on to researchers who publish their data on the CSH. Drafting a data management plan for epidemiological and clinical studies was another task for the data stewards involved with infrastructure.

Data stewards from disciplinary research – or researchers with the appropriate profile – had different roles. They assessed the RDM in place for the studies conducted by their research institute, highlighting which RDM strategy was already in place and which other parts of RDM were missing.

Additionally, their role involves testing the established standards and services, as well as soliciting feedback from research and the broader research community for the relevant study.

3 Aims

This pilot scheme aims to combine the knowledge of the infrastructure provider and the research party, i.e. a data steward from the infrastructure party should liaise with a researcher or data steward from the discipline-specific party. With this in mind, the initial aim was for both the data managers and the researcher to familiarise themselves with and gain a thorough understanding of each other's perspective. The infrastructure data steward would collaborate with the researcher or discipline-specific data steward to design an infrastructure that caters to the needs of the researchers at their institution. The discipline-specific data steward, being well-versed with the specific requirements of the researchers, offers valuable input on the necessary infrastructure. The two data stewards then jointly develop training formats covering basic RDM concepts and NFDI4Health services, such as the CSH, the publication policy and the metadata

¹ <https://csh.nfdi4health.de>

² <https://repository.publisso.de/resource/fr!%3A6431467>

schema. The goal of these training sessions was to educate researchers on RDM and equip them with the knowledge needed to input their studies (= study metadata) into the CSH. These training sessions also contributed to deliverable D4.5 “Cross-domain graduate education programme on research data management and data science” (Dierkes et al. 2023).

4 Approach and development of the data steward pilot

To better understand the current needs in both primary areas of NFD4Health, the pilot project was designed to run one pilot with epidemiological studies and another with clinical studies. The epidemiological pilot was conducted by ZB MED in collaboration with the University of Bonn, while the clinical pilot was conducted by the UCL Cologne in collaboration with the University of Cologne (figure 1).

4.1 ZB MED/University of Bonn (DONALD study)

The ZB MED data steward collaborated with a University of Bonn data steward involved in the Dortmund Nutritional and Anthropometric Longitudinally Designed (DONALD) study³, an epidemiological study which investigates diet, development, metabolism and health from infancy to adulthood. In a first step, the two data stewards exchanged at length to learn about each other’s respective working methods by creating a data management plan based on questions from a generic data management plan by the Research Data Management Organiser RDMO.⁴ This data management plan comprises more than 80 questions from categories such as thematic and technical classification of the research data, metadata, quality assurance, legal and ethical issues, reusability of data, and long-term archiving of the data. By going through the questions, the research-specific data steward informed the infrastructure-specific data steward about how data were handled within the DONALD study, while the infrastructure-specific data steward explained how RDM works and what strategies and tools could or should be used at different stages of a project. The initial questions were also adjusted to the DONALD study as some of them did not apply, while other questions needed to be devised for areas or workflows within the study which the existing questions did not cover. The generic metadata schema, which served as the basis for the repository developed by NFDI4Health, the CSH, was discussed intensively in addition to the joint development of the data management plan. The metadata schema was then jointly completed for the DONALD study and the metadata published in the repository. Based on practical feedback, identifying the necessary service adjustments and missing features, the metadata schema was optimised for open cohort studies. In addition, the University of Bonn and researchers from the DONALD study have given input on additional NFDI4Health services, including the publication guidelines, repository filtering and search functions, and training options (section 4.1.1).

³ <https://csh.nfdi4health.de/resource/45>

⁴ https://rdmorganiser.github.io/docs/RDMO-Fragenkatalog_nummeriert_201911.pdf

Figure 1: Communication path between data steward and researchers in the two pilot projects.

As pointed out in section 3, one of the aims for the two data stewards from ZB MED and the University of Bonn was to develop a joint training format on RDM.

Based on ZB MED training sessions for RDM in (bio-)medicine⁵, the two data stewards developed a training workshop for researchers involved with the DONALD study. The training consisted of fundamental concepts of RDM, such as research data, the research data life cycle, metadata, FAIR data principles, and guidelines on RDM, and was supplemented by NFDI4Health services. The data stewards from ZB MED presented the generic RDM concepts as well as the NFDI4Health services, and the University of Bonn's data steward complemented this by demonstrating how those concepts were realised in the RDM of the DONALD study. The slide deck from this workshop was published as an open educational resource so that other libraries and researchers can adapt it to their own requirements.⁶

The online course spanned two days, with each session lasting 90 minutes and was attended by 13 individuals. A feedback survey was conducted after the training and evaluated to enhance the course and better cater to the needs of researchers.

A few key points voiced within the feedback that have already led to and will lead to further adaptations to the training and training materials were as follows:

⁵ <https://repository.publisso.de/resource/fr!%3A6399944>

⁶ <https://repository.publisso.de/resource/fr!%3A6452640>

- *Some slides contained too much text:* The amount of text could be reduced; the information could be presented more visually with diagrams and graphical depictions
- *The workshop would be better in person:* Attempts should be made to arrange and hold future courses in person
- *There should have been more exercises and practical examples:* Further examples and exercises will be included so that the newly gained knowledge can be put into practice
- *It should be pointed out more clearly why RDM is important:* Tips on practical implementation will be added to not only inform participants about tools and procedures, but to state in what way they will be able to contribute by implementing the presented means
- *The researchers' needs should be given more consideration:* Further specialised training workshops on specific topics such as data management plans or how to fulfil the DFG's requirements on data handling⁷ will be designed and offered in the near future

4.2 UCL/Clinical Trial Centre

During the proposal's design phase, clinical trial centres (ZKS) were identified as important stakeholders for research data management. ZKSs are responsible for supporting clinics, departments, and institutes in planning, organising, and conducting clinical studies. Additionally, they serve as a central reporting point for clinical studies in compliance with the hospital's third-party funding guidelines. Therefore, they pool data stewardship skills and provide the network, i.e. access to the researchers conducting the studies.

While the ZB MED data steward collaborated with a project scientist in their data stewardship role, the UCL pursued an alternative approach to access clinical studies and researchers. By teaming up with another service provider, the aim was to pool skills, learn about the needs of researchers conducting clinical trials, and create tailored RDM learning solutions.

To establish a relationship, the UCL data steward organised several meetings with representatives of the ZKS and found it a challenge to identify the right person to talk to. An additional obstacle was that the concepts and understanding of research data management were very different. During clinical trials, treatments are planned with statistical precision and then reviewed and assessed systematically in a larger patient sample to ensure accuracy. This is the sole method of reliably determining the efficacy and tolerability of drugs, surgical techniques, or radiation. Thus, clinical trial centres are rigorously regulated environments because of the type of studies they undertake. Due to the nature of trials during which no changes can be made to the ongoing protocol, it proved to be impossible to gain access to or establish a contact for an ongoing trial. It is furthermore rather difficult to gain access to a study as a third party, since many of the trials are handled with the utmost confidentiality.

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https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/grundlagen_dfg_foerderung/forschungsdaten/forschungsdaten_checkliste_en.pdf

Direct access to the researchers was very difficult due to the ZKS's self-perception as the main service provider. Consequently, this presented an unintended competitive situation. While the data steward who acted as the point of contact for the DONALD study was part of the NFDI4Health network, there was no such person at the ZKS. It was challenging to engage with individuals since it was an unwelcome addition to their daily tasks, despite ZKS Cologne acknowledging the beneficial nature of the proposed services and training. For the future, it would appear to be important to involve the operational (and business and scientific) management more closely when implementing the pilot project in order to avoid unintentional competition and to make the added value clear. During further communication, it was discovered that project managers in the ZKS may be the right individuals to facilitate communication between the data steward and the clinical researchers. This approach will be included in the ongoing pilot scheme.

The data management plan discussed in section 4 was subsequently expanded and modified with the support of TA5 use case clinical trials and TA2 Standards. With the enactment of the DFG's data handling guidelines for research funding applications, clinical study researchers provided feedback on the need for aid in creating data management plans and ensuring data FAIRness. In clinical studies, a data management plan is part of the data management manual, along with the data handling report/data handling protocol. The data management plan outlines the tasks and their corresponding timelines, as well as the responsible parties. The document must include a comprehensive timetable for the study, detailing admission of the first patient, planned completion of the final examination of the last patient, the estimated duration for data evaluation, and any deviations from standard operating procedures (SOPs). In research data management, the term data management plan carries a nuanced definition in that it records the collection, structuring, publication, and long-term storage of all research data arising within a research project. It is relevant at every stage of a research project.

The data management plan was re-structured as per the categories recommended by the DFG. Building blocks in the form of response options will be included to aid researchers in writing their data management plan. The responses will, where appropriate, include links to the services provided by NFDI4Health, and provide additional details on the legal considerations related to the handling of data.

During the reporting period, an unplanned task emerged. TA3 develops the technical infrastructure of NFI4Health. As part of a decentralised federated infrastructure, Local Data Hubs (LDHs) provide structured storage and access resources for data-holding organisations, enabling interoperability within the NFDI4Health infrastructure. ZKS Cologne expressed an interest in this product, and an opportunity arose for the data steward to serve as an intermediary between ZKS as the customer and TA3 as the developer. In numerous software development projects, translating user needs into IT requirements has proven pivotal for project success and product acceptance. However, this activity is still in its infancy and will continue for the remainder of the data steward pilot project. Nevertheless, it is clear that establishing a local connection has benefits, including building trust.

The data steward pilot fulfilled the requirements of the NFDI4Health project by identifying the needs of researchers, specifically clinical trialists, and providing customised tools and standards to meet those needs. The pilot tested the generic data steward's knowledge of the data management plan against the expressed needs of the clinical trial investigators, resulting in the provision of a tailored tool.

As was the case with the ZB MED data steward pilot, it was clear in advance that awareness would need to be raised and training provided. Due to difficulties in locating suitable points of contact, an RDM training

session is yet to be held. Further feedback has shown that medical training is often constrained by time as personnel are occupied with daily clinical duties and other mandatory training activities due to regulatory requirements. This significantly diminishes the target group's inclination to take part in further RDM training. Raising awareness remains a significant challenge; thus, we concentrated on organising two information events for the medical faculty.⁸ The feedback from these events was highly favourable, leading to subsequent consulting inquiries.

In the meantime, the UCL data steward worked with the ZB MED data steward to conduct their training activities.

5 Results, lessons learned, conclusion

5.1 Institutional embedding of research-specific data stewards

An important result of the pilot involving two use cases was that it is essential to find the right contact person involved with research. While in the DONALD study it was clear from the outset that a person within the study would be selected as a counterpart to the data steward, it proved difficult to find the right contact person (counterpart) for the partner ZKS. The main reason for this is that a clinical trial centre is a service provider or infrastructure partner just like the library, in this case UCL Cologne (cf. Verbaan and Cox 2014).

In view of this, the two pilots are not easily comparable. However, this insight is valuable for future data stewards in a clinical context. Again, the clinical investigators need to be served directly by a data steward, not by a multiplier such as a clinical trial centre. It should be noted that even the many clinical trial centres at German universities or university hospitals are not easily comparable as their local organisational structure varies from place to place. The Association of Academic Coordination Centres for Clinical Trials (KKS/N) is a member of NFDI4Health, which presents an opportunity to compare experiences with other sites in the network as the pilot project progresses.

5.2 Competencies of the data stewards

A team of researchers investigated the competencies of data stewards at Austrian universities (Gruber et al. 2021). The authors subsequently compiled a list of competencies that data stewards should have in order to be successful in their respective fields. The competencies they identified can be divided into two categories: methodological and specialist skills on the one hand, and social and interpersonal skills on the other hand. Data stewardship is a highly service-oriented profession that requires data stewards to interact regularly with 'clients', i.e. the researchers they work with, so interpersonal skills are as important as professional skills. The actual competencies required by the data stewards described in this pilot project also depend on their respective profiles, i.e. whether they work in infrastructure or in research, as their professional knowledge will vary greatly. For an infrastructure-specific data steward, the methodological and technical skills listed in Table 1 are deemed essential.

⁸ [Information session](#) at the School of Medicine at the University of Cologne (22.06.2022) and a [GAMMA lunch seminar](#) for the medical faculty (26.09.2023).

The specialist skills required will mostly depend on the area in which the data steward works; for example, knowledge of research data management should be a prerequisite for a data steward working in infrastructure. The requisite methodological skills are largely independent of the data steward's background and result from the highly service-oriented nature of the data steward's role. Effective communication skills, including the ability to present information clearly, manage conflicts, simplify complex issues, and mediate between researchers and development teams are crucial when working with customers such as researchers, while problem-solving strategies can prove helpful when handling complaints or feedback from researchers. Effective management skills, including time management and knowledge management, are essential for structuring workflows and designing and delivering training workshops. Expertise in website design is beneficial for addressing researchers' inquiries and troubleshooting a service. Additionally, community engagement fosters a connection between the research community and data stewards, in turn allowing the latter to create valuable tools or solutions tailored to the needs of researchers and thus positively impacting the community.

Table 1: Necessary methodological and specialist skills for infrastructure data stewards	
Methodological skills	Specialist skills
Presentation skills (e.g. for training sessions)	Knowing the research practice
Conflict management	Research data management (RDM) knowledge
Problem-solving techniques	Basic programming knowledge
Explain complicated issues in a simple way	Basic librarian knowledge
Website design	Data privacy and sensitive data knowledge
Time management	Licensing and copyright knowledge
Ability to 'translate' (be a mediator)	Open Science and FAIR data principles
Community engagement	Knowledge in Digital Object Identifier (DOI) knowledge
Knowledge management	Experience in project application
	Basic public relations knowledge
	Basic database knowledge
	Good command of English
	Knowledge of funding guidelines

Additional social and interpersonal skills, as listed in Table 2, should complement professional skills. As previously mentioned, a data steward must regularly interact with researchers and service developers. Hence, it is crucial to possess social skills to cultivate a constructive conversational atmosphere. Effective communication skills, such as active listening and empathy, are important when engaging with both external stakeholders and colleagues within one's organisation. A helpful and persuasive approach forms the foundation of excellent customer service while promoting the institution's services and tools specifically designed for researchers. Good motivational skills can also benefit the promotion of services and encourage researchers to use them. As mediators between researchers and developers, data stewards should have team player skills and cooperative abilities since they collaborate with various departments to develop and enhance services based on researchers' feedback.

Table 2: Necessary interpersonal and social skills for infrastructure data stewards	
Interpersonal skills	Social skills
Technical affinity	Motivational capability
Willingness to engage in education and training	Helpfulness
Solution-oriented	Persuasiveness
Well organised	Empathy
Curiosity	Cooperative ability
Adaptability and flexibility	Mediate between development and research, collecting demands, 'translation' for development
Resilience	Good listener
Patience and persistence	Service-oriented
Communication	Team player
Tolerance	
Openness	
Creativity	
Talent for explaining issues (at different levels)	
Self-initiative	
Willingness to compromise	
Assertiveness	
Extrovert	

Aside from social skills, a data steward is also expected to have certain interpersonal skills. Technical expertise is useful when it comes to promoting and enhancing services. Being curious, creative, and open-minded is beneficial for maintaining a service and solution-oriented approach. A data steward is often responsible for creating and delivering training programmes. The ability to explain complex topics to individuals at various levels is crucial to ensuring participants (researchers) acquire the essential RDM skills. Furthermore, a data steward should display a willingness to learn new skills, as well as educate themselves in areas where they lack knowledge. Problem-solving is a critical part of a data steward's role. Skills like resilience, patience and persistence are especially helpful when troubleshooting and teaching researchers how to make use of services. Assertiveness and a willingness to compromise are necessary to arrive at solutions to errors or feedback, whenever possible. Tolerance and adaptability are valuable characteristics when seeking and discussing innovative and effective solutions. As data stewards may be requested to deliver talks or training sessions at conferences or other events, an extrovert personality facilitates networking and enables them to confidently address researchers and participants.

5.3 Future data steward profiles

It is evident that both profiles are necessary and complement each other. The extent to which fundamental knowledge can be merged into one individual in the future relies on the availability of training opportunities. One option could be to provide training for researchers in the role of data steward on the fundamentals of RDM. This could be accomplished through a certification course akin to the one presently available in North Rhine-Westphalia (e.g. Slowig et al. 2023).

Training a generic data steward in the basics of a discipline would appear to be more difficult as this would require at least a bachelor's degree in that discipline. Liaising between an infrastructure data steward and a research data steward therefore seems appropriate given the current situation.

6 References

- Dierkes, Jens, Fürst, Julia, Hörner, Tanja, Klammt, Sebastian, Lindstädt, Birte, Pigeot, Iris, Restel, Katja, Schmidt, Carsten Oliver, Waltemath, Dagmar, Zeleke, Atinkut, 2023. Training concepts in research data management and data science with the focus on health research. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006441348>
- Gruber, Alexander, Hermann Schranzhofer, Sabrina Knopper, Sarah Stryeck, and Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi. 'Kompetenzen von Data Stewards an österreichischen Universitäten'. *Mitteilungen der Vereinigung Österreichischer Bibliothekarinnen und Bibliothekare* 74, no. 1 (1 September 2021). <https://doi.org/10.31263/voebm.v74i1.6255>.
- Seidlmayer, Eva, Fabian Hoffmann, Jens Dierkes, Birte Lindstädt, Ralf Depping, and Konrad Ulrich Förstner. 'Forschung unterstützen - Empfehlungen für Data Stewardship an akademischen Forschungsinstitutionen'. Application/pdf. Köln: ZB MED Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften, Universität zu Köln, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006441397>.
- Shutsko, Aliaksandra, and Birte Lindstädt. 'Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur für personenbezogene Gesundheitsdaten – NFDI4Health: Pilotprojekt zu Bibliotheken und Forschungsdatenkompetenzzentren als Multiplikatoren („Data Steward“)''. *GMS Medizin - Bibliothek - Information* 20, no. 3 (22 December 2020): Doc27. <https://doi.org/10.3205/mbi000484>.
- Slowig, Benjamin, Blümm, Mirjam, . Förstner, Konrad, Lindstädt, Birte, Müller, Rabea, and Lanczek, Marvin. 'Der Zertifikatskurs „Forschungsdatenmanagement“ Als Blaupause ür die FDM-Bezogene Kompetenzentwicklung Im Rahmen Der NFDI'. *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure* 1 (7 September 2023). <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.268>.
- Verbaan, E., and A. M. Cox. 'Occupational Sub-Cultures, Jurisdictional Struggle and Third Space: Theorising Professional Service Responses to Research Data Management'. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship* 40, no. 3 (1 May 2014): 211–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2014.02.008>.